

Identifying modes of interaction in dance-music collaborations

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Abstract

This research project investigates the relationship between the mediums of sound and movement, in the context of interactive music performance, through a conceptual interpretation of symbiosis, a phenomenon describing the close and persistent interactions between organisms of different species. Mirroring the types of symbiosis that manifest in nature, sound-movement interactions are qualified three distinct modes, identified according to the collaborating practitioners' intended outcomes, provisions, operation, and cognition of affect. In this paper, the symbiotic framework is used as means of designing the mappings for a live work, as well as an analytical tool towards understanding the dancer's role as part of the music-making process. For the latter, six dancer-musician collaborations from the field of interactive dance are analysed, with the accounts provided by their authors revealing the emergence of multiple modes in each work, as well as examples of mutation between different modes over the course of a performance. It should be noted that the limited availability of case studies with sufficient information for this analysis highlights the need for further insight of the collaborative process within literature focusing on HCI-mediated composition, particularly accounts of how technological tools are utilised, understood, and appropriated within our collaborators' dance practices. The symbiotic framework offers this opportunity by abridging complex concepts into prompts using nomenclature that is shared between the disciplines of music and dance, thus presenting a more efficient and inclusive approach in communicating the potential and limitations presented by HCI tools to non-specialist users.

1. Introduction

Technologically mediated interaction between the artistic mediums of sound and movement is a topic that in recent years has received rigorous attention. Over the course of more than half a century, specialised research communities have gone to develop a wealth of novel outcomes in areas such as Digital Musical Instruments, sensor technologies, interaction design, mapping strategies, data sonification and compositional processes. More often than not, the primary motivation behind these research outcomes is to exploit scientific knowledge towards expanding the expressive possibilities of artistic practice. Such creative outcomes have given rise to the specific practice of interactive performances, most often developed in collaboration with disciplines utilising physical movement as their principle expressive medium, such as performance art and dance.

This type of interdisciplinary collaboration can be traced from ancient times, with music and dance understood to have developed a complementary relationship, one where several features are shared, yet still “mean” differently, as Rachel Duerden (74) notes:

The closeness between the two announces a relationship... linking two disparate entities in a way similar to metaphor highlights a clear point of contact between them, but it also invites to consider additional connections.

Duerden expands on this observation by arguing that much of the audience reaction to simultaneously witnessing dance and music derives from the unconscious processing of the differences and similarities between the two artforms. What is of particular interest to this paper is the author’s comment on a dancer’s articulating a rhythmical pattern that is also heard in the composition:

we immediately notice the correspondences between them, correspondences that offer a sense of the two events belonging or coalescing in some way. We perceive the movement reaching 'closure' with the sound. The movement could, almost, be the cause of the sound we hear. But we know that it is not...

In Duerden’s example, it may well be the case that sound is not caused by sound. However, the field of interactive dance has for some time produced outcomes where movement can very much control sound, owing to the emergence of interactive technologies where motion sensing devices allow the imprinting of choreographic features within digital media. This technological development has gone to not only redefine the relationship between the two disciplines, but has also brought along additional layers of complexity that pose further barriers in the communication between collaborating practitioners.

The research presented in this paper aims at simplifying the concepts behind Human-Computer Interaction tools, or more specifically, how these technologies are applied in the context of live works featuring technologically mediated interaction between dance and music, for the purpose of communicating these concepts to non-specialist audiences, who often are our dance collaborators.

2. Dance-music relationship

Considering the definition of interaction as the ‘interplay between two equal parties’ (Siegel & Jacobsen 29), it could be concluded that an interactive performance is one where ‘the dancer influences musical processes while the music in turn affects the performer’. However, the vast majority of the related literature focuses its contributions in the areas pertinent to technology and music, while revealing little about the role of the choreography. Furthermore, equally often the musician is presented as the source of technological innovation, who provides the knowledge in the specialised tools necessary to implement technologically mediated interaction. Taking this broad generalisation at face value, the reached conclusion is that dancers are simply not enthusiastic about technology, with the experts ‘spending more time introducing people to working with computers... [than] doing creative work’ (Horwitz). Of course, this is simply not the case, as evident from the rich field of dance technology, which employs and explores scientific knowledge to a degree at least as high as that observed in the field of music. From this discussion, the emergent questions concern the role of the dancer in our own field’s literature; do dancers need to become proficient in the language of the technologies driving our musical expression in order to exploit their expressive potential? does

music affect movement the same way as movement affects music? is there truly equality in the interaction between our mediums? and if not, is that something we should strive for?

Having collaborated with more than twenty dancers and performance artists over the past ten years, while our practice focused on performances featuring real-time interactions between sound and movement, my research has been investigating those questions through Practice Research and autoethnographic methodologies. Acknowledging both the vast differences and undisputed connections between music and dance, I placed my experiences as an electronic musician and dance collaborator against a ‘conceptual debate’ with a biological mechanism which enables strong bonds between disparate individuals; that is the phenomenon of symbiosis. And while our early practice used the term as little more than a title alluding towards the harmonious coexistence of two entities, further research on the phenomenon revealed a much more complex relationship between “collaborating” species. And in many ways, similar complexities are noted in the relationship between dance and music.

Art historian Andrew Uroskie (227) comments on this relationship:

music was understood to govern the movement of the dancers. Choreography, within this propulsive conception, was a kind of musical interpretation, judged on its ability to form a singular synaesthetic coherence in the experience of the audience

In discussing the seminal collaboration between composer John Cage and choreographer Merce Cunningham, Uroskie sketches the traditional process in dancer-musician collaboration, which implies that the composition of music precedes that of dance, and serves as a platform on which the choreography can be then developed in a synaesthetic manner. This tradition was all but eliminated by Cage and Cunningham in the 1965 *Variations V*, which is one of the earliest performance works to feature technologically mediated interaction. Dancers’ movements initiated an array of tape machines that contained Cage’s sonic palette (Miller). But as Uroskie points out, the dancers were not in conscious control of the sonic palette, as that would entail that ‘one model of subordination would have merely been exchanged for another’ (229).

From this description, it can be concluded that despite the interaction between sound and movement, the two mediums were neither subordinate to each other, nor either were tasked with propulsive duties, but instead coexisted in an “autonomous equilibrium”. Beyond Uroskie’s commentary, and with the hindsight of over 50 years of technological advances, a less poetic assessment of the interaction design in *Variations V* could conclude that the lack of conscious control was the result of the crude for today’s standards motion sensors, which afforded a limited scope for extracting precise movement data.

Nowadays, with HCI technologies affording us that precise control, propulsion in sound movement interactions is once again evident, albeit reversed. Setting aside techniques such as auditory scene analysis and other non-real-time technologies commonly used in dance practice, recent research outcomes demonstrate a tendency towards using movement data extracted from the choreography as sources of modulation for the sound generating devices. In comparison with the original observation of ‘choreography, [as] a kind of musical interpretation’ before the rise of interactive technologies, sound in these recent works can be described as a kind of gestural interpretation.

Considering Uroskie’s conceptualisation of ‘subordinate’ artistic mediums exploited towards ‘propelling’ that of their counterpart discipline, a useful investigation is not to make a case in favour of one type of subordination, but rather look at the causes of this relationship; interaction

entails the creation of emergent elements in one domain resulting from the actions conducted in another, and as a result, requires that one of the interacting parties will affect its counterpart. In the context of the interactive performances in question, the only means of interpreting sonic elements into choreographic expression are the dancers' own cognitive mechanisms. On the other hand, composers are able to exploit a range of motion capture and gesture recognition devices by which they can extract detailed movement data, and use these towards modulating real-time composition systems. As a result, an inherent dependency emerges, with sound being technologically propelled by movement. However, dependency neither implies subordination in a particular direction, nor does it describe a permanent and static status in the relationship between two elements, as evident by the conceptual topic of this paper, symbiosis.

3. The symbiotic habit

The lexicological definition of symbiosis suggests two elements existing in a sustained harmonious relationship. However, in the context of biological associations, harmonious coexistence is merely one of the many manifestations of symbiotic relationships, and one that must be gained through hard work and dedication. To summarise the biological phenomenon, symbioses are defined as relationships that are close, persistent, and interspecific, meaning involve organisms of two or more species (Paracer & Ahmadjian). The engaged organisms are identified as the host and its symbiont, with the relationship most often initiated by the symbiont becoming attached to the typically larger host, as a way of seeking protection, nourishment, or any other beneficial outcome to its fitness. And since the symbiont is always benefited, it is the effect on the host which defines the type of symbiosis. When the host experiences a negative fitness outcome, the relationship is parasitic, when there is no significant harm or benefit, it is commensalistic, and mutualism describes a mutually beneficial relationship. It is important to note that the three types of relationship describe dynamics as they are observed at a particular moment in time, with research having established an evolutionary trajectory (Douglas). Relationships that are mutually beneficial to both host and symbiont are seldom the result of a fortuitous meeting between organisms with complementary traits. Instead, today's observed mutualisms have emerged from parasitic relationships; starting with a symbiont motivated to seek a host for exploitation, prolonged interaction causes a parallel adaptation of both organisms' biological traits as to allow both to extract benefit from each other (Yong).

So, what links can be drawn between symbiosis and collaboration in artistic practice? Firstly, biologists often use collaboration as a metaphor for symbiotic relationships, and in fact both types of cooperation share the same intentions, that of overcoming one's limitations. And the stipulation that symbioses need to be interspecific, points towards collaboration across disciplines. Moving forward with this interpretation, the organisms within a symbiosis can be understood as the collaborating practitioners, the distinct species of the organisms as the respective disciplines of each practitioner, and each species' biological traits can be related to the artistic mediums of each discipline. Then, the roles of host and symbiont can be related to the roles of instigator and directee that often emerge in collaborations. This particular interpretation provides a further link between the two domains.

Quite like symbiosis, collaboration also manifests across a spectrum (Hayden & Windsor), ranging from directive to collective, with each type defined according to the level of shared creative influence between the engaged practitioners (illustrated in figure 1). For example, a composer-performer collaboration can range from the composer writing a score which the

performer has to closely adhere to, thus being a directive collaboration, to the composer providing a more open set of instructions that can be freely interpreted by the performer, thus the end result being a collective creation. With symbiosis also manifesting across a spectrum depending on the host's fitness outcome, the different types of symbiosis can be understood as the different types of collaboration, with each type defined according to the level of creative input or expression allocated to the directee. And while the previous example concerns intradisciplinary collaboration between music composer and performer, in the context of dance music collaboration, fitness outcome is related to the range of movement that the interaction design allocated to the dancer, thus completing the interpretation. This interpretation is illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 1: types of symbiotic relationships related to types of collaborative practices

With the symbiotic interpretation providing some insights into the different ways collaborations can be organised in respect to their practitioners, the same concept can be applied towards identifying a taxonomy of interaction between sound and movement. As mentioned earlier, the typical approach in interactive dancer-musician performances is using movement data towards controlling and modulating the sound generating system. Therefore, with sound being dependent on movement, it can be understood as the symbiotic artistic medium, with movement being the host that governs or propels the relationship. Considering that in symbioses a host can be benefited, harmed, or unaffected, thus determining the type of the relationship, the range of movement allocated to the dancer from the interaction design goes to define the mode of interaction between the two mediums. For example, a design aiming to produce a specific sonic outcome through a predetermined set of gestures and body positions, poses the greatest level of restrictions on a dancer's movements, similar to the instructions involved in a typical choreographic work. On the opposite end of that spectrum, a work designed around indeterminate sonic outcomes can potentially allow a dancer to freely improvise without any restrictions, while largely ignoring the interaction, and rather inform their movements from the produced sound. Finally, in the middle of that spectrum emerges a mode where dancers can control sounds of predefined textures and morphologies, but of indeterminate arrangement and levels, thus resembling a performance involving structured improvisation, where sonic outcomes can be approximated, or anticipated.

Symbiotic relationships		Interdisciplinary collaborations	
organisms	symbiont	instigator	practitioners
	host	directee	
interspecificity	biological traits	expressive media	interdisciplinarity
fitness outcome		expressive range	

Figure 2: interpretation of symbiotic relationships as a model for interdisciplinary collaborations

From those connections a framework begins to take form (illustrated in figure 3), qualifying each mode according to the movement’s provisions, acting as the cause, and the sonic outcomes being the resulting effect. However, for each provision to match its intended outcome, the necessary process is the system’s operation by the dancer. In my experience, explaining how an interactive system operates through HCI terminologies, such as the distinction between instrumental and algorithmic mappings (Salter et al), or the notion of transparency or legibility of interaction, can often confuse practitioners whose specialism lie in different domains. Instead, the framework is using neutral terms that can be understood from the perspective of both involved disciplines, as with the previous descriptors that are shared between dance and music practices. Operations are described as exploration, detachment, and instruction, each suggesting the dancer’s ideal frame of mind while interacting with the system in each mode. The final element of this framework concerns the dancer’s level of understanding of and familiarisation with the system, or in other words, the level of awareness of how their movements can affect sound. In the case of an instructive mode, only a moderate level of awareness is required, as the dancer can rely on the choreography which has been designed with producing specific sonic outcomes. A detached operation can be performed without requiring any familiarisation with the system, something which can potentially be counterproductive when the aim is an indeterminate outcome. Finally, exploration sits on the opposite side of the spectrum, with the performer required to possess an intimate understanding of how movement will affect sound, and act akin to a musician recalling specific sounds from their instrument at will.

	Interaction modes		
	<i>Mutualism</i>	<i>Commensalism</i>	<i>Parasitism</i>
Affect awareness	high	low	moderate
Provision	structured improvisation	free improvisation	score/ choreography
Operation	exploration	detachment	instruction
Outcome	anticipation	indeterminacy	determinacy

Figure 3: framework for “symbiotic” modes of interaction between sound and movement

4. Case studies

It is worth mentioning that the findings informing this framework emerged from developing the performance *Symbiont Zero*. That is a duet for dancer and electronic musician, originally developed alongside contemporary dancer Shona Roberts, and was then performed with four other dancers. This work has been previously detailed alongside three precedent case studies, each selected as to illustrate a particular mode of interaction (Moriarty 2020a). Following a previous publication (Moriarty 2020b), the framework here is used to perform a similar analysis of six works that feature dancer-musician collaboration and technologically facilitated interaction between sound and movement. Of course, the sample list is not exhaustive insofar works involving dancers and musician collaborations, but rather I opted to include papers that provide sufficient details describing the dancers' provision, operation, and affect awareness, as well as the nature of the sonic outcome. And as discussed in the conclusion, seeking suitable accounts was an unexpected challenge.

4.1. Digital Dance Project (Siegel & Jacobsen)

This early work describes the allocation of control to parameters that are perceptible yet do not require "excessive concentration on instrumental performance". While the composers describe each section's sonic characteristics in detail, they also point out a degree of freedom on the arrangement borne out of the dancers' interaction, thus suggesting an outcome of anticipated textures and structure. The authors also describe the dancers' positive feedback in feeling "freedom in the direct relationship between movement and music" with "fairly transparent or direct relationships between the dancer's movements and their musical consequences", pointing towards the high level of affect awareness. Besides this degree of freedom, the final work requires the dancers to follow a set of choreographic instructions.

4.1. Arroyo/Aura/Trio de Cuatro (Morales-Mazaneres et al)

Traversing a labyrinth through motion-activated sonic clues suggests exploratory operation, with the previous knowledge of specific sound cues, albeit triggered over an indeterminate arrangement, relating to the notion of anticipated outcomes. At the same time however, the authors mention that "it is important for dancers to learn the musical consequences of their movements", thus pointing towards a high affect awareness. And although the utilised system SICIB is designed towards 'improvisation', in the context of the three described works, a pattern of structured improvisation emerges, following a predefined rule-based exploration of the dancers' environment.

4.2. Raja (Ahola et al)

In Raja, a choreographer designed the dancers' movements following a briefing of the composers' intentions and possibilities presented by the system. Following the initial rehearsals with the interactive system, the dancers commented that "the sounds were somewhat irresponsive, predictability was weak", suggesting a high level of affect awareness. However, although described as largely choreographed, the work also features a section with improvisation accompanied by "familiar piano sounds" as opposed to the "electronic sound set in the beginning and end parts", something which allowed the now improvising dancers to

better process the slow-paced soundscape towards developing their movements. As such, a mutation of modes is evident, with the first and third parts requiring the dancers to follow a determined choreography, while the middle part's provision that of improvisation, consequently affecting the operation to that of exploration and the outcome to anticipation.

4.3. Emovere (Jaimovich)

The 'dynamic and unpredictable soundscape' resulting from the sonified electrocardiography (ECG) data points towards an indeterminate outcome. Considering the opaque connection between the dancers' movements and the sonic output, in combination with the largely involuntary bodily data measured by the ECG sensors, it can be concluded that the dancers possessed a low level of affect awareness, with their movements informed purely by the sonic output rather than a conscious engagement with the mapped parameters.

4.4. OtoKin (Dahlstedt & Dahlstedt)

In describing the performative aspects of OtoKin, the authors explain that they 'did not use explicit choreographed movements, but... allow for exploration of various movement patterns within the sound space'. As such, any predefined structure followed by the performers relate to the conceptual narrative of the choreography, rather than any adherence to a determined sonic arrangement, thus suggesting an improvised provision and indeterminate outcome. The utilised system allows for a degree of improvisation within each section, and 'lends itself well for both improvisatory exploration, and for semi-prepared narratives'. In regards to affect awareness, the work displays high level of awareness, with the added novelty of configuring onset points according to not only movements of the body itself, but also its topography within the dance space.

4.5. Vrengt (Erdem et al)

Vrengt focuses on the dancer's release technique, which places importance to 'flow procedures'. In order to make best use of this technique in the context of an interactive performance, the composers utilise a sonification system as a 'more objective approach to rendering sound in response to data than more creatively based sound design'. However, although this may suggest an indeterminate outcome, the authors describe the performance as a 'comprovisation', where 'the composed aspect of the instrument and choreography provide a large amount of freedom in collectively exploring sonic interaction through the performance', which points closer to an anticipatory outcome. In regards to system operation, this exploration becomes a focal point for the dancer, with 'listening as the main source for decision making, while intuitively moving along with a physical play and exploration'. This relates to the mode of exploratory operation, further supported by a high level of affect awareness, with the dancer having developed 'a gestural repertoire' through a 'sophisticated control of her movement, and hence sound'.

5. Conclusions

As stated in the introduction, this paper aimed to present an efficient and inclusive manner of communicating the principles and creative potential of HCI-mediated interactive performances. The symbiotic framework does not claim to have discovered any new modes of interaction; instead, it collects the existing approaches that have been developed within the field, and presents them arranged across a qualifiable spectrum which employs language that is shared among the disciplines of music and dance. This holds the potential of efficiently communicating complex concepts, and as a result, facilitate clarity in communication, something which is particularly welcome during the complex and intense process of artistic collaboration.

The symbiotic framework is less useful when the intention is to provide a thorough understanding of interactive systems. As well as applying on a fairly narrow area of interactive works (dancer-musician performance with real-time sound generation), there is little context on the technology facilitating the interaction, nor the cultural background of such practices. Of course, possessing knowledge in those areas is necessary for the field's practitioners. Can the same be said for everyone engaging with interactive works? In my experience, my collaborators have often viewed detailed technical descriptions as cryptic and alienating, and counterproductive in allowing them to think of potential avenues for engaging their material with HCI tools. Similarly, omitting any description can become a barrier for engagement between the two practitioners, resulting in a directive collaboration where the musician acts as the gatekeeper of technology, while the dancer is less-well equipped to conceptualise the developing work in line with the affordances of interactive technologies. With the framework focusing on the principles of operating interactive interfaces, it succeeds in filling the gap between 'too-much-information' and 'no information-whatsoever' by delimiting the range of potential avenues for implementing interactive strategies in performance. As a result, it allows our collaborators to actively participate in the development of the work, while also serving as a gateway for practitioners aiming to further their practical skills in technologically mediated practices.

To return to Rachel Duerden's quote from the beginning of this paper, she describes the relationship of dance and music as one 'steeped in metaphor', inviting practitioners to 'consider the potential transfer of attributes from one to the other'. She further points out the value of allegorical debates between the two disciplines as a way of highlighting their common ground: 'Linking two disparate entities by metaphor first draws attention to a clear point of contact between the two, and then goes further and implies or invites us to consider further connections'. In this presentation, the intersecting language between dance and music makes up the highlighted points of contact between the disciplines, which emerged from conceptualising collaboration as an allegorical symbiosis. Although a highly subjective endeavour which at times verges on being a poetic novelty, the concept is best viewed as a playful provocation, a new way of thinking the relationship between collaborating practitioners and their respective mediums of artistic expression. Nevertheless, the presented interpretation is informed by a significant body of rigorous scientific knowledge. And with the biological phenomenon being far more complex than what the brief summary presented here may suggest, it holds great potential for exploring further lines of inquiry in relation to creative practice, collaborative or otherwise.

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